

ISic3374

Funerary inscription for Athano

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

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Autopsy

2013.10.03

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Menae

Place of origin (modern)

Mineo

Provenance

Found in the vicinity ('contorni') of Mineo

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 38271

Physical Description

A large rectangular slab of coarse grey stone, roughly cut on all sides, with some damage to the face at the left margin

Dimensions

Height 42.5 cm

Width 74 cm

Depth 12 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-3: 70-125 mm

Interlineation

Not measured: mm

Text

1. Ἀθανοι

2. χρηστὰ

3. χᾶϊρε

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Athano, a worthy lady, farewell!

Commentary

The female name Ἀθανώ is attested on at least seven occasions, primarily in the eastern half of the Mediterranean according to LGPN [http://classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/lgpn_search.cgi?name=Ἀθανώ]

Digital identifiers:

TM 645602

EDCS 60800081

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 337

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Photo J. Prag